

CYCLOPES - Fighting Cybercrime – Law Enforcement Practitioners’ Network

Deliverable 5.5

4th Annual CYCLOPES Community Building Report

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Contributor(s)	Rashel Talukder
Reviewers(s)	ZITiS MUP

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1. Summary

One of the main goals of the CYCLOPES project is to build, strengthen and maintain links with initiatives, actions, and projects relevant to CYCLOPES, as well as learning and developing from the collective efforts, where possible. Since the last report D5.4 3rd Annual CYCLOPES Community Building Report, CYCLOPES' activities have been focussed on implementing targeted activities that actively involve practitioners, researchers, industry representatives, and other relevant stakeholders. The partners of the CYCLOPES consortium have used their available means to reach end users from LEAs, relevant stakeholders, academia and industry.

This report D5.5 “4th Annual CYCLOPES Community Building Report” describes the main results achieved in the period from May 2024 to April 2025.

2. Introduction

A broad and active community is essential in building an open network for experienced practitioners' working in the field of fighting cybercrime in Europe. However, there are already many institutions, networks and other initiatives focused on these domains that are relevant for the CYCLOPES project.

Aside from the internal LEA community, composed of Consortium partners, CYCLOPES forms a bridge between the project and: 1) EU and international organisations, such as EC, EC3, Europol's Innovation Hub, Interpol, ENISA, etc. 2) Networks of practitioners, especially ENLETS, ENFSI, i-LEAD, iLeaNet, EU-HYBNET and i-ProcureNet 3) networks and relevant stakeholders related to cybersecurity 4) research, industry, ethical and social societies and organisations.

In the first year of the project implementation, a methodology as a starting point for establishing relations with the relevant stakeholders was developed. The CYCLOPES Community Building Framework and Governance model (D5.1) defined the methodology, by which over the course of this 5-year-project, all members of the CYCLOPES community work together to reach the goals, ambition and objectives of the project.

3. Overview of main achievements: 4th year (May 2024 – April 2025)

During the first year, most actions have evolved around gaining awareness and visibility; the second year, focused on the implementation, so the team invited and motivated practitioners and other stakeholders to have a more practical hands-on experience with the CYCLOPES activities. In the third and fourth year, these activities continued with an emphasis on community building and strengthening connections.

The project builds, strengthens and maintains links with key stakeholders and networks indicated in the Figure 1, who work in the areas relevant to CYCLOPES:

Figure 1 Cooperation with other relevant stakeholders

As part of ongoing commitment to strengthening the fight against cybercrime, the CYCLOPES Consortium has continued to deepen collaborations with key stakeholders across Europe. This has been achieved by maintaining an active engagement with major entities such as the European Commission (DG HOME), EJCN, EACTDA, ECTEG, ENFSI, ENLETS, and the EUROPOL Innovation Lab. Through regular exchanges of information on current and upcoming activities - ranging from workshops and surveys to high-level conferences – the project ensured that efforts remained aligned. This synchronization helps prevent duplication of work and fosters greater efficiency across the various European networks involved in cybersecurity.

3.1. Key stakeholders

The project has ongoing communication and exchange of information about events and ongoing activities with the following key stakeholders:

- a. European Commission, DG HOME (D.4. Security in the digital age). The Commission's Directorate-General for Migration and Home Affairs is responsible for the EU's internal security policy, which is a component of the new Security Union Strategy 2020-2025. The aim is to build a safer Europe by fighting terrorism and organised crime by promoting police cooperation and by preparing to swiftly respond to emerging crises. DG HOME actions in this area include stricter rules against illicit trafficking of firearms and on trafficking in human beings, as well as revision of legislation on combating child sexual abuse, sexual exploitation and child pornography.¹
- b. European Union Agency for Criminal Justice Cooperation (EJCN). EJCN was established to foster contacts between practitioners specialised in countering the challenges posed by cybercrime, cyber-enabled crime and investigations in cyberspace, and to increase the efficiency of investigations and prosecutions. The EJCN facilitates and enhances cooperation between competent judicial authorities by enabling the exchange of expertise, best practice and other relevant knowledge regarding the investigation and prosecution of cybercrime.²

¹ https://commission.europa.eu/about-european-commission/departments-and-executive-agencies/migration-and-home-affairs_en.

² <https://www.eurojust.europa.eu>.

- c. European Anti-Cybercrime Technology Development Association (EACTDA). The purpose of the Association is the development of technological solutions for European Law Enforcement Agencies and Forensic Laboratories for their fight against crime.³
- d. European Cybercrime Training and Education Group (ECTEG). ECTEG is composed of European Union and European Economic Area Member States law enforcement agencies, international bodies, academia, private industry and experts. The primary aim of the working group is to provide experience and knowledge to further enhance the coordination of cybercrime training, by identifying opportunities to build the capacity of countries to combat cybercrime through the development and delivery of a robust and enduring training programme.⁴
- e. European Network of Forensic Science Institutes (ENFSI). ENFSI was founded with the purpose of improving the mutual exchange of information in the field of forensic science. This, as well as improving the quality of forensic science delivery in Europe, has become the main issue of the network. Besides the general work in the fields of quality and competence management, research and development and education and training, different forensic expertizes are dealt with by 17 different expert working groups.⁵
- f. European Network of Law Enforcement Technology Services (ENLETS). In ENLETS 29 members from across Europe are brought together to address and action shared priorities. ENLETS enables the sharing of best practices on a broad level, engaging on mutual priorities and stimulating future projects that can help fill the gaps and the known issues facing law enforcement of its members. The environment promotes collaboration and fosters a supportive network, working to help each other through current challenges.⁶
- g. EUROPOL Innovation Lab. The Lab aims to identify, promote and develop concrete innovative solutions in support of the EU Member States' operational work. This will help investigators and analysts to make the most of the opportunities offered by new technologies to avoid duplication of work, create synergies and pool resources.⁷
- h. International Criminal Police Organization (INTERPOL). INTERPOL is an international organization that facilitates police cooperation and provides investigative support, expertise and training to law enforcement worldwide, focusing on three major areas of transnational crime: terrorism, cybercrime and organized crime.⁸
- i. EU Agency for Law Enforcement Training (CEPOL). CEPOL is an agency of the European Union that builds a network of training institutes for law enforcement officials in EU Member States and supports them in providing frontline training on security priorities, law enforcement cooperation and information exchange. CEPOL also works

³ <https://www.eactda.eu/index.html>

⁴ <https://www.ecteg.eu/>

⁵ <https://enfsi.eu/>

⁶ <https://enlets.eu/>

⁷ <https://www.europol.europa.eu/operations-services-and-innovation/innovation-lab>

⁸ <https://www.interpol.int/en>

with EU bodies, international organizations and third countries to ensure that the most serious security threats are tackled with a collective response. The agency's annual work programme is built with the input from this network and other stakeholders, resulting in topical and focused activities designed to meet the needs of Member States in the priority areas of the EU's internal security strategy. Moreover, CEPOL assesses training needs to address EU security priorities. CEPOL constantly strives to offer innovative and advanced training activities by integrating relevant developments in knowledge, research and technology and by creating synergies through strengthened cooperation.⁹

3.2. CYCLOPES Community Members

One of the CYCLOPES' key goals is to build and maintain an innovation-driven network of European law enforcement agencies and experts specialised in combating cybercrime. Different techniques and platforms are commonly used to engage with the CYCLOPES communities. Some of them are designed specifically to share information, while others aim to successfully involve practitioners, industry and researchers in relevant activities'.

A core priority of CYCLOPES has been the strategic expansion of the network. Thanks to proactive outreach, CYCLOPES Community now includes approximately 250 dedicated practitioners committed to combating cybercrime from countries shown in Figure 2. It is possible to join the CYCLOPES Community after signing up on <https://cyclopes-project.eu>, (via click on the JOIN US button). This page provides a snapshot of the project and what members can expect from the support of the initiative.

Figure 2 CYCLOPES network geographical regions

Specific members of the CYCLOPES community are involved in the project activities through participation in the practitioners' workshops, annual dissemination workshops, webinars and

⁹ <https://www.cepola.europa.eu/>

other relevant activities. Moreover, CYCLOPES is in continuous contact with all community members to synchronise and define the CYCLOPES priority topics for the following years.

3.3. CYCLOPES Community building activities'

The CYCLOPES team has dedicated efforts to enlarge the community and attends various events and meetings across Europe. By participating in the following key events and meetings across Europe, **CYCLOPES has strengthened connections, established strategic partnerships, and exchanged valuable insights with related projects and stakeholders.**

- Security and Policing Event 2024 on 12th – 14th March 2024 in UK.
- EACTDA meeting on 13th – 14th March 2024 in Lisbon.
- European Clearing Board meeting on 10th and 11th April 2024 in Brussels.
- 14th InfoCom Security Conference “The Hybrid World of Cybersecurity” on 10th – 11th April 2024 in Athens.
- EC3 Cyber Innovation Forum 2024 on 18th and 19th June 2024 in The Hague.
- CERIS Annual Event 2024 on 24th and 25th September 2024 in Brussels.
- CITNiA 2024 Conference on 24th to 26th September 2024 in Krakow.
- RISE-SD 2024 on 16th and 17th October 2024 in Chalkidiki.

While we have already built strong relationships with several EU-funded initiatives, we remain committed to exploring new opportunities for collaboration and knowledge sharing.

3.4. ENLETS Messenger Service (EMS)

A part of the community building activities is focused on cooperation with the use of communication and collaboration platforms developed or used in other networks. This provides an ideal opportunity to exploit the efforts of these initiatives and to spend time on establishing links and building relations, rather than the considerable time and resources required to develop such communication channels.

ENLETS has offered a dedicated space for the CYCLOPES Community on their ENLETS Messenger Service (EMS), where practitioners can chat, collaborate on work-related topics and establish relations. This solution provides a safe, encrypted chat experience through a dedicated mobile application and web browser service. CYCLOPES currently uses a dedicated channel for internal communication as well as ENLETS provides a ‘general’ channel for sharing information about the upcoming events and relevant outcomes.

4. Upcoming and planned community building activities

In the coming months of the implementation, the project will continue the collaboration with key stakeholders as well as research projects and other initiatives in the area of fighting cybercrime. To effectively manage community building, we are organising an event on 17th - 18th June 2025 in Warsaw in collaboration with EACTDA, ECTEG and Europol Innovation Lab. This event will focus on challenging the capabilities of tools and gathering evidence using AI-powered systems in a dynamic scenario. This medium-sized gathering will bring together up to 50 highly specialized representatives from LEAs, fostering targeted collaboration and real-world application.

5. Conclusion

This document described how the building up of the CYCLOPES Community is managed and summarized the results achieved in the period from May 2024 to April 2025. This report may

also have informative value for other stakeholders to build greater awareness of the planned CYCLOPES activities and foster synergies.

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